

THE NEED TO RESEARCH AND USE ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE RESEARCH

Sindarova Sh. M.¹

¹Assistant Engineering and Computer Graphics
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry

Rikhsibaev U. T.²

²Associate professor Engineering and Computer Graphics
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry

Khalilova H. E.³

³Senior lecturer Engineering and Computer Graphics
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034684>

Keywords: Creativity, thinking, fluency, flexibility, accuracy, originality, cooperation, tasks, playful technologies.

Abstract: This article provides methodological guidelines for the development of students' creative research. Effective methods of increasing students' knowledge level are pedagogically highlighted.

Creativity is considered a very important methodical potential for students of a higher educational institution. Increasing the value of modern education and science in the society is related to the expansion of the requirements for the level and quality of knowledge. Further development of students' creativity is one of the main tasks that we have set before us. The development of knowledge, worldview and interests is based on the production of innovative new ideas. It consists in the development of human abilities and skills to produce any new innovative ideas. Therefore, it is necessary and necessary to develop creativity in students, to form creativity.

Increasing interest in the development of creativity in various fields leads to new innovations. Thus, one of the qualities that make up the CREATIVITY model of Human Development is critical thinking, cooperation, creativity, creativity and communication. International research organizations define creativity as one of the basic skills needed in modern life and emphasize the need to develop creativity as part of the integration of academic education and professional training.

The nature of the demand for strong professionals shows the relevance of such qualities as creativity: the ability to work in a team and independently, to solve problems, to search for new methods. It is to determine the conditions for the development of students' creativity in the process of studying in higher

educational institutions. Qualitative research is informed by in-depth expert interviews with experts in higher education. The analysis of recent studies on the topics of youth employment, the problem of inconsistency between the higher education system and the labor market shows that creativity in the context of higher education is considered as an integral feature, its main features are specific g represents the ability to generate ideas, result orientation, solving practical problems, originality and speed of thinking, openness to innovation and creativity.

The frequency of using the term "creativity" in the development plans of Uzbekistan's economy is increasing, the importance and necessity of changes in the national education system to ensure the effective development of creativity among students in educational institutions is emphasized. The concept of creativity At the current stage of the development of society, one of the main tasks of education is the development of human capital as the most important resource of the modern economy.

Despite the fact that one of the main factors of the growth of human capital is its creative element, science has not yet formed a consensus on the conceptualization of creativity. Creativity: is defined as a multi-purpose cognitive creative ability and its four main characteristics should be highlighted: fluency, flexibility, precision and originality. Creativity that sustains and develops ideas in students is sensitivity to problems, lack of knowledge, harmony, search for answers and solutions, putting forward hypotheses, testing them and increasing the quality of the process of forming results. We consider creativity in relation to the needs of the individual: the higher the level of demand, the higher the creativity. Creativity is inherent in every person, but many people lose it under the influence of various factors. The connection between creativity and social values is one of the most important and leading needs and values of a person - self-development, self-expression, and the desire to develop one's potential. Openness to innovation, the ability of non-standard solutions, security of the external environment, freedom of self-expression are conditions for the realization of potential, self-development. Many scientists have studied the creative qualities and creativity of a person and are still studying it.

A creative act consists of three systems: an individual, a field of activity (general practices, values, knowledge) and a community of experts, that is, a community of people who carry out their professional activities in this field. According to some scientists, the basis of creativity is the generation of a number of ideas that

can be options for solving a particular problem. Based on experience and knowledge, a person chooses the most appropriate solutions, and it eventually becomes the final product. It also states that creative ideas cannot be defined using certain measurement parameters without identifying non-creative ideas. Of course, to carry out such a process, not only experience and knowledge are needed, but also a number of certain skills and qualities.

In addition, there are approaches to the definition of creativity, which include a set of previously formulated definitions: 1. "Creativity is the combination of perceptions realized in a new way, the ability to find new connections, the emergence of new concepts;

- relationships;
- tendency to create and recognize innovations;
- the activity of the mind that leads to new concepts;
- experience of changes in a new organization;
- imagining new categories of meanings.

Creativity and education can be viewed from different perspectives. One of the approaches to the study of creativity in education is related to the introduction of the competence approach, which is based on the consideration of creativity as the interdependence of several components: methodological, procedural, personal and panoramic.

According to this approach, creative competence is the ability to work effectively and inventively in conditions of uncertainty to solve specific practical problems, knowledge and experience, readiness to flexibly use the acquired knowledge, self-discipline and self-discipline. improvement.

Depending on the topic, creativity in education is studied in four aspects: personal (students and students' creativity), group (communication, cooperation), procedural, institutional (factors and environmental conditions). All studies that have any influence on the development of creativity-related abilities and personality traits have noted the importance of culture, environment, and other conditions. Promoting creative economy, human capital and innovation requires cooperation between higher education, economy and cultural policy. Skills, knowledge, attitudes do not develop in a vacuum, they always differ depending on the field, so the question of developing creativity is primarily a question of the fields of application.

Research on the issue of creativity in collaborative teams has shown that proximity can be beneficial for group creativity, if perspective is not taken into account. The main opportunities for the development of creativity during

studies at the university are educational activities and a favorable climate, curriculum. A number of researchers are concerned that despite the fact that higher education institutions play an important role in the changing world, modern educational programs do not meet the needs of the economy and the labor market, and the development of creativity is not sufficiently evaluated and studied.

Development of student creativity in higher educational institutions: Creativity of students is related to creativity of teachers. Teachers' level of creativity is related to how they rate students' creativity-related traits, i.e., the more creative a teacher is, the more students' creativity-related traits, leadership, and perception are related to creativity. While students define creativity mainly as a characteristic of a person or process, professors understand student creativity in terms of self-reflection, independent decision-making, curiosity and motivation, and the production and development of new things. We must recognize the great influence of tutors and socio-cultural systems in the development of students' creative culture. But in pedagogy, the importance of students' creativity is underestimated, since it is a central issue. At the same time, students play one of the most important roles in the educational process, so this issue should not be neglected in the process of improving student qualifications. Training affects idea generation, creativity of solutions and leadership effectiveness. The introduction of educational methods into education opens up the creative possibilities of students. In the modern world, there is a need for professionals who are able to create new ideas, who are in high demand, who form innovative models and propose and implement competitive projects. The success of such activities is mainly ensured by the high creative ability of specialists.

The great creative potential of young people, developed and implemented in a perfect and methodical manner, will bring great benefits to the state. However, it is a difficult problem to determine the vector of development of student creativity in universities in time and skillfully form it. The unstable position of the educational system is due to the lack of a systematic, conceptual approach to education. Research on ways to develop students of higher education also shows that the expert opinions of university management and business leaders state that modern higher education should be both fundamental and practical.

The use of interactive, playful, educational methods and forms in the educational process is noted as an important factor in the development of students' creativity. The most effective of these methods and forms are the ones that are

so close to practical activities: practical tasks, cases, scientific games, conferences, strategic sessions, conversations, seminars. In addition, it can be performed as a course work, diploma, and qualification work, and they can be directed not only to students, but also to specialists in a certain field. One of the highest potentials for the development of creativity is the scientific and research work of students, in which a practice-oriented, problem-oriented approach is fully implemented. The activity of the institute is one of the main elements in the mechanism of production of research activities of universities and gathering of new knowledge. Experts say that the study of humanities develops the ability to think creatively, increases the cultural level, and forms the human value-semantic basis. An important factor in the development of creativity is interpersonal relationships, especially with teachers. The effectiveness of the educational process depends on the teacher's interest in professional activity. The ability to think, analyze, synthesize information and make decisions, it is difficult to implement changes at the global, systemic level in educational processes. Another important factor in the development of creativity among higher education professionals is the creation of conditions to contribute to the stimulation of creative processes in the university environment. The process of creativity development must include the social strengthening of creativity, communication with people who have creative abilities, and the creation of conditions in which there is a positive example of creative behavior.

He prefers to organize events that provide interpersonal and intergroup communication: excursions to enterprises, organizations, meetings with experts, conferences, roundtables, etc.

Analyzing the thoughts of students, creative research allows to determine whether the educational environment, as a rule, is aimed at developing the qualities characteristic of creativity, including openness to new impressions, the ability to abandon stereotypical ways of solving problems. Highlighting the most developed quality among students - the creation of many original ideas and strategies that are clear, general, radically different from stereotypes, focusing on expanding opportunities.

This means that the creative potential inherent in young people requires that it be opened by specialists and teachers. This fact is connected with the need for a more thorough and demanding selection of teachers, as well as training in the technology of working with students aimed at identifying creative talent and a targeted, individual approach to creative talent. It is recommended that students

use more practical activities with game elements that develop their creative abilities.

The modern era of society's development is characterized by changes affecting all spheres of human activity. In such conditions, society's need for an independent creative person is increasing. In this regard, socio-economic reforms are placing high demands on higher education in terms of practical preparation of higher education students to continue their studies and engage in work.

For example: science, technology and production. Orientation to the development of the personality of modern higher education students, his knowledge and creative abilities shows his creative development in the overall educational process. It is necessary to educate students not in the old way, but using new technologies, using a new level of training of teachers. but also update without hesitation. He only occasionally refers to modern concepts of developmental education and, in particular, competence-oriented technology.

The innovative development of talent is the provision of high-quality general education that meets the modern requirements of society and every citizen. This is to create conditions for the development of creative and scientific potential of students, identify creative and talented students, accompany them and support them.

CONCLUSION : Nowadays, the urgent problem of university education is to improve the professional training of graduates of pedagogical universities. First of all, its high social significance and uniqueness - the personal identity of the student is connected with the formed personality.

References:

1. Рихсибоев, У. Т., Халилова, Х. Э., & Синдарова, Ш. М. (2022). AutoCAD дастуридан фойдаланиб деталлардаги ўтиш чизиқларини қуришни автоматлаштириш. *Science and Education*, 3(4), 534-541.
2. Ортиков, О. (2022). DISTANCE EDUCATION TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM. *Журнал интегрированного образования и исследований*, 1(1), 1-7.
3. Mirzaliev, Z., Sindarova, S., & Eraliyeva, S. (2019). Organization of Independent Work of Students on Drawing for Implementation of the Practice-Oriented Approach in Training. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 17(1), 297-298.
4. Renessans, O. (2021). IQTIDORLI TALABALAR BILAN SHUG'ULLANISH METODIKASI.(MUHANDISLIK FANLARI MISOLIDA). *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(8), 32-39.

5. Ортиков О. Оптимизация натяжения нитей на ткацких станках с микропрокладчиками //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2017.
6. Bobomurotov, T. G., & Rikhsiboev, U. T. (2022). Fundamentals Of Designing Triangles Into Sections Equal 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17 And 19. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, 3(2), 96-101.
7. Abdug'aforovich, M. A. (2022). METHODOLOGY OF STUDENT CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT IN TEACHING ENGINEERING GRAPHICS. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 22, 557-560.
8. Abdurahimova, F. A., Ibrohimova, D. N. Q., Sindarova, S. M., & Pardayev, M. S. O. G. L. (2022). Trikotaj mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarish uchun paxta va ipak ipini tayyorlash va foydalanish texnologiyasi. Science and Education, 3(4), 448-452.
9. Ортиков О. Dynamics of plane motion of a rigid body //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2021.
10. Sindarova, S. M. (2021). O'YINLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI O 'QUVCHILARNING BILIM, KO 'NIKMA VA MALAKALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH (CHIZMACHILIK FANI MISOLIDA). Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(11), 686-691.

